

RISC++: A 32-bit RISC-V Core via High-Level Synthesis of C/C++

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Abstract—As hardware design shifts towards custom architectures, custom-made Central Processing Units (CPUs) emerge as a mechanism to provide more efficient hardware amidst ever-growing demand. However, the traditional design process may introduce difficulties when the Instruction Set Simulator (ISS) and the Hardware Description Language (HDL) code are defined in different abstraction levels, and not intrinsically correlated. This may lead to divergences between these two components of the design, slowing production down. A more efficient method for the development of these systems is possible through High-level Synthesis (HLS), where a program written in a high-level programming language can be converted into HDL. With this in mind, we propose the creation of a C/C++ codebase that serves for instruction set simulation and also for HLS. This method may avoid production problems and considerably reduce necessary hardware developer expertise when creating a custom RISC-V CPU, without compromising the end product.

I. INTRODUCTION

In digital hardware design, current High-Level Synthesis (HLS) tools present themselves as a competitive alternative to traditional Register-Transfer Level (RTL) design flows. In HLS, code written in high-level languages such as C++ can be used to generate Hardware Description Language (HDL). This level of abstraction is often desirable, as it eases development, maintainability and verification of hardware-defining code. HLS tools are particularly advantageous for designing accelerators, as designers can focus on the code’s functionality and not on architectural details.

Still, a typical custom CPU design flow, as shown in fig. 1 does not involve HLS. Normally, it requires the maintenance and verification of two separate codebases: one for RTL representation, usually written in languages like Verilog or VHDL, and another for instruction set simulation. Instruction Set Simulators (ISSs) are greatly used for software validation when the actual hardware implementation is not available. However, the development and maintenance of two parallel codebases can sometimes lead to production problems or slowdowns, since it must be ensured that both codebases represent the exact same functionality.

II. BACKGROUND

This section details some important concepts in HLS and introduces the RISC-V instruction set architecture.

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Fig. 1. Typical custom CPU design flow.

Fig. 2. Proposed HLS-based CPU design flow.

A. High-Level Synthesis

High-Level Synthesis is an automated process that can read an abstract behavioral model of a digital system and produce an RTL structure that realizes that behavior. This method of digital hardware design is widely used for creating custom accelerators for heterogeneous processing systems [1]. In fact, HLS tools are particularly efficient for designing computing-heavy hardware that can benefit heavily from parallelism and pipelining [7].

Since the high-level code is removed from concepts like clock timing and synchronization, an HLS tool must be able to infer data dependencies and time hardware operations correctly. Modern HLS tools do this by compiling the code into a formal model, then creating a data and control flow graph of the code and allocating available hardware resources towards scheduled, pipelined operations [2].

In HLS, a pipeline is characterized by the number of clock cycles between two consecutive operations: the Initiation Interval (II). It is important to note that HLS tools always schedule operations for the worst-case scenario. This means that a pipelined loop's II will be limited by the circuit's critical path. An II value of one is usually desirable, but may also be difficult to achieve due to data dependencies or tight hardware constraints.

Since multiple circuits can be designed to perform the same function, the HLS design process requires designers to provide additional specifications to the tool. These specifications include design constraints, such as available FPGA resources, as well as design directives. Design directives guide the tool on how to allocate hardware resources and schedule operations. Different tools may use these directives in various ways. For example, in Xilinx's Vitis HLS environment, designers can use `#pragma` commands to define operations like loop unrolling and pipelining, array partitioning, and function inlining.

B. RISC-V

RISC-V is an open standard based on Reduced Instruction Set Computer (RISC) architectural principles, meaning that the RISC-V Instruction Set Architecture (ISA) is characterized by a streamlined set of simple instructions. The RISC-V standard contains a multitude of extensions designed for different purposes, e.g., the M extension for integer multiplication or the F extension for floating-point operations.

Interestingly, the RISC-V standard defines a dedicated opcode space for custom extensions, where they can define their own instructions. This allows designers and engineers to create highly specialized processing hardware that still adheres to a generalized architectural standard.

This level of flexibility and adaptability, coupled with cost-effectiveness due to the absence of licensing fees, make RISC-V highly attractive for researchers and engineers alike.

III. DESIGN OF A CPU VIA HLS

This section highlights different strategies, advantages and challenges when designing complex control-oriented hardware

like CPUs using current HLS tools, and how these problems may be circumvented.

A. Advantages of HLS

Leveraging HLS for processor design is not a completely new endeavour, even if it is relatively unexplored. Many existing designs have pointed out the ease of design and implementation when compared to traditional RTL design flows [7], [4]. Some authors also note a considerable gain in development time and reduction in required developer expertise, while still generating results comparable to cores designed in HDL. Together, these factors lower the barrier of entry for custom processor design [7].

B. Design challenges

A first approach to creating a processor unit via HLS may be to develop a simple switch-based ISS, and use it as source code for HLS. This would work, but it is unlikely to generate competitive hardware. Current tools are unable to design an efficient processor pipeline from a simple ISS [7].

This is mainly due to the data dependencies inherent to this situation. An example is calculating the next program counter value. The next iteration's program counter can be determined by different parts of the datapath, depending on the current loaded instruction. Additionally, if the current instruction is a branch instruction, the branching condition must be evaluated, resulting in nested data dependencies. All of this generates a long critical path, which inevitably produces large II values.

C. Strategies for designing performant hardware

Because of these problems, a simple ISS program won't generate efficient hardware. The ISS must be modified in some way such that the generated pipeline does not suffer as much from these data dependencies. Other HLS-based cores have circumvented this by explicitly programming the pipelining stages into the high-level code, and using HLS directives to ensure proper timing and II constraints [4], [7]. Some designs even employ support for branch prediction, multi-cycle instructions, and pipeline control features such as stalling, forwarding and flushing.

This means that current HLS methods can't completely erase some architectural complexities in designing a processor core, because these optimizations still have to be considered and programmed into the source code and cannot be automatically inferred by the tool.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF RISC++

We propose *RISC++*, a 32-bit RISC-V core written entirely in C/C++, which is currently under development. Compiling the *RISC++* source and a simple testbench program with g++ produces an ISS executable. This executable can receive two hex files as inputs: one mandatory hex file for the code memory which contains the program to be simulated, i.e., RISC-V binaries produced with conventional compilation via the RISC-V GNU toolchain [5] and an optional hex file for the processor's data memory.

To generate a hardware implementation, the same code, assisted with minor preprocessor macros and HLS `#pragma` commands, can be fed to Xilinx’s Vitis HLS to produce synthesizable HDL. Currently, this core can be instantiated as a kernel function in an FPGA target, and the same hex files are loaded into its program and data memories through code running on the host machine. Currently, only the RV32I architecture is implemented, but support for other extensions is planned.

RISC++’s code takes advantage of C++’s object-based nature and organizes different processor blocks as classes. For example, the decoding step is defined as the constructor of the `DecodedInstruction` class, which populates the class’ variables according to the raw data bits fetched from memory. Additionally, it contains a `MemoryController` class that organizes memory access and an `ALU` class that executes integer operations.

As listing 1 shows, the main CPU loop is divided into three main steps: fetch, decode and execute.

```

1  main_cpu_loop: while (running) {
2      // fetch
3      instruction_bits_t undecoded_instruction = memc.
4      fetch(rf.pc);
5
6      // decode
7      DecodedInstruction current_instr(
8      undecoded_instruction);
9
10     // execute
11     execute(current_instr, &rf, &memc);
12
13     // update running condition
14     running = isRunning(undecoded_instruction, rf.pc
15     );
16 }

```

Listing 1. The main CPU loop

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

To ensure proper validation of the core, the `riscv-tests` repository [6] has been cloned and adapted so that we are able to generate compatible hex files executable by RISC++. These adaptations are heavily based on the testing work done by B. Goossens [3]. `riscv-tests` is a macro-based testing suite, so macros have been adapted to exclude system calls and unsupported operations. Then, a single assembly program named `_start.S` runs all 38 tests sequentially. Test results are written to data memory addresses larger than `0x2000`. If a memory byte located in these addresses is not null, a test has failed.

The software testing environment contains a simple testbench also written in C++ that reads the hex files and calls RISC++’s top-level function, named `riscpp`. A condensed version of this testbench is shown in listing 2.

The hardware testing environment consists of an x86 host machine that configures the Programmable Logic of a Xilinx Alveo U250 board connected via a PCIe port, as fig. 3 demonstrates. The host machine then runs the `testbench.c`

Fig. 3. Current testing environment.

program which consumes compatible hex files, in the same way as the ISS. It’s important to note that the `testbench.c` file that runs in the host machine during hardware testing is not the same as the software testbench that is compiled by `g++`, since the hardware testbench must communicate with the Xilinx Alveo U250. However, these testbenches provide very similar functionality and consume the same hex files.

Currently, software validation correctly executes 35 of the 38 tests present in the testing suite. Once software validation is complete, we aim to begin conducting synthesis work and hardware validation, as well as developing more features, such as support for common RISC-V extensions and a 3-stage pipeline.

```

1  int main(int argc, char* argv[]) {
2
3      uint code_ram[CODE_RAM_SIZE] = {0};
4      uint data_ram[DATA_RAM_SIZE] = {0};
5
6      char* codeFilename = new char[strlen(argv
7      [1])+1];
8      strcpy(codeFilename, argv[1]);
9      loadHexFile(codeFilename, code_ram);
10
11     if (argc == 3) {
12         // data hex exists
13         char* dataFilename = new char[strlen(
14         argv[2])+1];
15         strcpy(dataFilename, argv[2]);
16         loadHexFile(dataFilename, data_ram);
17     }
18
19     uint instruction_counter = 0;
20
21     riscpp(0, code_ram, data_ram, &
22     instruction_counter);
23
24     ramDump(code_ram, data_ram);
25 }

```

Listing 2. The software testbench’s main function

VI. CONCLUSION

This work presents the ongoing development of *RISC++*, a 32-bit RISC-V core designed entirely using High-Level Synthesis (HLS) from C/C++ code. The project demonstrates the potential of HLS to streamline the CPU design process by

integrating instruction set simulation and hardware description into a single codebase. This approach simplifies development and reduces the expertise required for hardware design, addressing some of the key challenges faced in traditional Register-Transfer Level (RTL) design flows.

Our preliminary results highlight several advantages of using HLS for processor design. HLS enables rapid prototyping and iteration by allowing high-level language code to be directly converted into HDL, thereby facilitating easier maintenance and verification. This integration significantly reduces the complexity associated with managing parallel codebases for simulation and hardware implementation.

However, our work also reveals challenges, particularly in managing data dependencies and optimizing pipelining and execution intervals. These challenges require careful architectural planning and the strategic use of HLS directives to guide the synthesis process.

As the development of *RISC++* continues, our focus will be on completing the software validation, conducting synthesis work, and performing hardware validation. Future efforts will also include the implementation of additional RISC-V extensions and the development of a more advanced pipeline architecture. This project aims to further demonstrate the viability of HLS in CPU design and contribute to the broader adoption of high-level synthesis techniques in the digital hardware design community.

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